

Exploiting In-Hand Knowledge in Hybrid Joint-Cartesian Mapping for Anthropomorphic Robotic Hands

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Abstract—In this extended abstract, we propose a novel hybrid approach that combines both joint and Cartesian mappings in a single solution. In particular, we exploit the a priori, in-hand information related to the areas of the workspace in which thumb and finger fingertips can get in contact. This allows to define, for each finger, a zone of transition from joint to Cartesian mapping. The proposed hybrid mapping is presented and experimentally evaluated with a real slave anthropomorphic robotic hand.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teleoperation of anthropomorphic robotic hands is still lacking of a general practical solution, notwithstanding the great technological advances in control and algorithms in the field of telerobotics during the last decades [1]. In literature, related works can be classified in two human to robot hand mapping subproblems: (i) measurement, tracking and identification of human hand motions; (ii) mapping of human hand motions to the robotic hand. In the context of the present study, we will not focus on the first problem, which has been solved with good results by several sensor equipments, such as sensorized gloves, marker-based/marker-less vision systems or hand exoskeletons, along with advanced calibrations procedures [2]. We will therefore focus on the second problem, for the reason that it is a both conceptual and analytical problem which still lack of a general solution [3].

In this work, we propose a hybrid joint-Cartesian mapping exploiting an aspect poorly explored in previous works: the in-hand information available a priori. Specifically, we consider the areas of the master and slave hand workspaces in which the contact between thumb and finger fingertips is possible, and we exploit this constructional knowledge to realize a smooth transition between joint and Cartesian mappings. The exploitation of fingertips contact areas has been poorly investigated in previous hand mappings, although the importance of the thumb-finger workspace intersections is well known from specific studies [4], and we claim that it can be used for improving the mapping of motions from the master hand to an anthropomorphic robotic hand.

II. METHODS

A. Joint-Cartesian Mapping Transition

Considering only the thumb and index finger without loss of generality, in the proposed method we want to realize that a

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master-to-slave Cartesian mapping is in place when both index and thumb fingertips are inside the hand workspace region in which their fingertips can get in contact, delimited by the convex hull ${}^M H$, i.e. the set of points $B_{{}^M H} \supseteq {}^M H$, whereas outside such region a joint mapping is enforced. It follows that also the definition of a transition region between the two kinds of mapping needs to be introduced.

Considering the centroid ${}^M g$ of ${}^M H$, let $\widehat{{}^M H}_s$ be the scaling of the convex hull ${}^M H$ by a scale factor s . Consequently, $B_{\widehat{{}^M H}_s}$ will denote the region of the master hand workspace delimited by $\widehat{{}^M H}_s$. We also define the set $B_H = B_{\widehat{{}^M H}_s} \setminus B_{{}^M H}$, containing all the hand workspace points corresponding to $B_{\widehat{{}^M H}_s}$ that does not belong to $B_{{}^M H}$. Exploiting multidimensional interpolation using radial basis functions (RBF) for the computation of an interpolant function f , it is therefore possible to consider, for the master hand, a *thumb transition* $f_T = f({}^M p_T)$ and an *index transition* $f_I = f({}^M p_I)$, where ${}^M p_T$ and ${}^M p_I$ are the Cartesian position of the thumb and index fingertips, respectively. Finally, we define the *thumb-index transition* function $f_{TI}(f_T, f_I)$, or simply f_{TI} , as

$$f_{TI}(f_T, f_I) = \begin{cases} f_T, & \text{if } f_T \leq f_I \\ f_I, & \text{if } f_T > f_I \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) allows us to have a transition value belonging to the interval $[0, 1]$ without discontinuities for all ${}^M p_T, {}^M p_I \in B_H$.

Collecting the Cartesian position and orientation in a single fingertip pose vector for both thumb and index

$${}^S x_{T,Q} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{T,Q} \\ {}^S o_{T,Q} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad {}^S x_{I,Q} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{I,Q} \\ {}^S o_{I,Q} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

from the application of the forward kinematic results that ${}^S x_{T,Q} = {}^S \mathcal{F}_T({}^S q_{T,Q})$ and ${}^S x_{I,Q} = {}^S \mathcal{F}_I({}^S q_{I,Q})$. Similarly, if we put in the case of Cartesian mapping, we consider that the thumb and index fingertip poses ${}^S x_{T,C}$ and ${}^S x_{I,C}$ are available, according to the notation

$${}^S x_{T,C} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{T,C} \\ {}^S o_{T,C} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad {}^S x_{I,C} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{I,C} \\ {}^S o_{I,C} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where ${}^S p_{T,C}, {}^S p_{I,C}$ are the Cartesian positions and ${}^S o_{T,C}, {}^S o_{I,C}$ the orientations of the slave thumb and index fingertips, respectively, as directly available from the application of the Cartesian mapping.

Then, referring to the generic slave hand thumb and index finger joint values as ${}^S q_I$ and ${}^S q_T$, respectively, it is possible to think them as given by the related inverse kinematics functions as

$$\begin{aligned} {}^S q_T &= {}^S \mathcal{I}_T({}^S x_{T,input}), \\ {}^S q_I &= {}^S \mathcal{I}_I({}^S x_{I,input}), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

with

$$x_{T,input} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{T,input} \\ {}^S o_{T,input} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad x_{I,input} = \begin{bmatrix} {}^S p_{I,input} \\ {}^S o_{I,input} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

and where ${}^S p_{T,input}$, ${}^S p_{I,input}$ and ${}^S o_{T,input}$, ${}^S o_{I,input}$ are thumb and index Cartesian position and orientation inputs, respectively. We therefore impose, according to our mapping approach, that for the position inputs

$$\begin{aligned} {}^S p_{T,input} &= (1 - k_{TI}) {}^S p_{T,Q} + k_{TI} {}^S p_{T,C}, \\ {}^S p_{I,input} &= (1 - k_{TI}) {}^S p_{I,Q} + k_{TI} {}^S p_{I,C}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where k_{TI} is a smooth, sigmoidal gain described by

$$k_{TI} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } {}^M p_T, {}^M p_I \notin \widehat{B_{MH_s}} \\ 1, & \text{if } {}^M p_T, {}^M p_I \in B_{MH} \\ \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos(\pi f_{TI})) & \text{if } {}^M p_T, {}^M p_I \in B_H \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Instead, for the orientation input we impose $o_{T,input} = o_{T,map}$ and $o_{I,input} = o_{I,map}$, where

$$o_{T,map} = \begin{cases} {}^S o_{T,Q} & \text{if } k_{TI} = 0 \\ {}^{SM} o_T & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

$$o_{I,map} = \begin{cases} {}^S o_{I,Q} & \text{if } k_{TI} = 0 \\ {}^{SM} o_I & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where $o_{T,Q}$ and $o_{I,Q}$ are from eq. (2), whereas ${}^{SM} o_T$ and ${}^{SM} o_I$ are the orientations of master thumb and index fingertips with respect to the master finger base reference frames, consistently described with respect to the slave index and thumb base reference frames. Specifically, let ${}^M R_{o_I}$ and ${}^M R_{o_T}$ be the rotation matrices – with respect to the related master finger base frames – associated to the index and thumb fingertip orientations o_I and o_T , respectively. Then, ${}^{SM} o_I$ and ${}^{SM} o_T$, in eq. (9), will be the orientations of master index and thumb – with respect to the related slave finger base frames – associated to the rotation matrices ${}^{SM} R_{o_I} = R_{SM_I} {}^M R_{o_I}$ and ${}^{SM} R_{o_T} = R_{SM_T} {}^M R_{o_T}$, respectively, where R_{SM_I} and R_{SM_T} compensate for different orientation of slave base-frames/fingertips with the respect to the master when the hands are in home configuration.

Eqs. (6)–(7) allow to have a smooth transition, with a spatial sigmoid-like profile and without discontinuities, from joint to Cartesian mapping and vice versa for the slave hand thumb and index. If ${}^M p_T$ and ${}^M p_I$ are located in the master hand’s workspace region delimited by the convex hull ${}^M H$, a Cartesian mapping is enforced, whereas a joint mapping is imposed if ${}^M p_T$ and ${}^M p_I$ are outside of the region delimited by $\widehat{M H_s}$. Finally, a transition takes place when both the master thumb and index fingertips cross the transition region corresponding to the set of points B_H , following eqs. (6).

Fig. 1. Mapping of grasps on the real UBHand. (a) Large ball and (b) large cylinder. (c) Pencil and (d) coin.

Fig. 2. (a) Volar grasp application: pouring mock-up liquid from a bottle. (b) Precision grasp application: drawing a line with a marker.

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

Test with the real UBHand: We tested the mapping using the real UBHand as slave robotic hand, as reported in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Note that, also in this experiment, the master hand was simulated, and its predefined motions were directly mapped to the real slave hand using the proposed method. Referring to Fig. 1, it can be observed the grasping of a series of objects with the UBHand. Specifically, we have carried out: (i) two volar grasps (objects “large ball” and “large cylinder”) and (ii) two precision grasps (objects “pencil” and “coin”). Fig. 2 shows video frames during the performance of a volar grasp application (pouring of mock-up liquid from a bottle) and a precision grasp application (drawing a line with a marker).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this extended abstract a hybrid joint-Cartesian mapping based on in-hand knowledge of the master and slave hands has been proposed for anthropomorphic robotic hands.

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